

Short Chain Free Fatty Acids as Putative Pheromones in the Marking Fluid of Tiger

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*Manuscript received 9 October 1990, revised 18 March 1991,
accepted 24 April 1991*

SHORT chain free fatty acids (FFA) play an important role in chemical communication of various mammals¹⁻⁴. In the mongoose² and in the monkey³ this role is rather definite and in the human⁴ it is suggestive.

On the basis of 9662 ejections of 'marking fluid' (MF) of ten tigers in open air zoo of Nandankanan (Orissa) we have now evidence that MF is an agent for chemical communication^{5,6}. Having established that MF contains FFA, traceable even in the tiger cub⁷, we now report the identification and quantitative estimates of FFA in tiger MF.

MF, collected at site, was brought to the laboratory either under hexane or in ice to prevent bacterial degradation and stored at -70° . An aliquot of the MF (removing hexane layer whenever necessary) was just acidified with 0.5 N H_2SO_4 and steam-distilled. The distillate was rendered alkaline with a few drops of 1N NaOH and dried under reduced pressure at 60° and the FFAs were regenerated by dropwise addition of 5N H_2SO_4 under ice and extracted with diethyl ether (3×0.5 ml). The pooled ether extract was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and subjected to analysis by glc on a stainless steel column (3 m $\times$ 3mm i.d.) packed with 10% FFAP and 1% H_3PO_4 on 100-120 mesh chromosorb W(HP) using a Hewlett-Packard 5840A instrument using FID detector and integrator : column temperature, 150° ; carrier gas, N_2 with at a flow rate of 33 ml min^{-1} ; injection port and detector were kept at 200° .

The peaks on the chromatograms were identified by comparing the t_R values with those of authentic compounds (Aldrich). Help was also taken of the plots of $\log t_R$ vs carbon number of the fatty acid molecules. The sample was hydrogenated in dry methanol in presence of Adam's catalyst (PtO_2) and rechromatographed under similar conditions as in the cases of the original samples to identify unsaturated components.

Although no unsaturated FFA could be traced, 14 major saturated FFA were identified (in a particular sample): acetic (73%), propionic (3.6%), isobutyric (1.6%), butyric (0.7%), isovaleric (0.4%), valeric (1.2%), isohexanoic (0.4%), hexanoic (7.7%), isoheptanoic (1.0%), heptanoic (1.6%), isooctanoic (1.3%), octanoic (2.0%), isononanoic (0.6%) and nonanoic (4.5%) acids.

In urine and anal gland secretion of various animals so far studied^{1,2}, FFA upto six carbon atoms have been detected. In the tiger MF, we have now also identified the hepta-, octa- and nonanoic acids and the corresponding isocompounds. Very recently the presence of hepta- and octanoic acids have been reported in the anal gland secretion of aardwolf⁸.

Acknowledgement

Financial support from DOEN is gratefully acknowledged. The authors are also indebted to

Prof. S. Ghose, Department of Biochemistry and the staff of Lipid Chemistry Laboratory, Bose Institute, Embryology Unit, Indian Statistical Institute and Nandan Kanan Biological Park, Orissa for generous help and cooperation.

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